

Comparative Assessment Of Role Of Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste, Calcium Hydroxide And Curcumin In Pain Reduction During Endodontic Treatment: An In Vivo: Visual Analog Scale Study

Mansi Singh¹, Anurag Jain², Aruna Kanaparth³, Sonal Bansal⁴, Srishti Chaturvedi⁵, Priya Hora⁶

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Post Graduate Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Professor²
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Professor And Head³
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Reader⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Post Graduate Student⁵
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Post Graduate Student⁶
Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry & Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Abstract

Background: The most frequent cause of pain is the existence of bacteria brought on by improper canal disinfection. Therefore, the primary goal of endodontic therapy is to eradicate these microorganisms as completely as possible. Intracanal medications have been recommended as between appointment dressings to eradicate any leftover microorganisms following root canal therapy and lessen tissue inflammation at the periapical level.

Aim- The aim of this study was to evaluate and compare the efficacy of Modified Triple Antibiotic Paste, Calcium Hydroxide & Curcumin as an intracanal medicaments in post operative pain reduction using Visual Analog Scale (VAS).

Material and Method: Sixty four maxillary central incisors, lateral incisors or canines with a chief complaint of pain and planned for root canal treatment were randomly selected and were further divided into four groups. Group I (n-16) control group, Group II (n-16) receiving calcium hydroxide, Group III (n-16) receiving triple antibiotic paste and Group IV (n-16) receiving curcumin as an intracanal medicament. Pain was measured using visual analogue scale (VAS). The scores were recorded preoperatively, at 24 hours, till 7th day. The result was tabulated and statistically analysed.

Results: At baseline, the mean score pain for all four groups were in the same range. There was no statistically significant difference between the preoperative mean pain score values. Group III showed the highest pain reduction followed by Group IV, Group II and Group I respectively.

Conclusion: Within the limitation of this study it can be concluded that Modified Triple antibiotic paste showed effective pain control as an intra-canal medicament.

Introduction

Endodontics is the branch of dentistry that deals with the etiology, prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases and injuries affecting the dental pulp and periapical tissues.¹

The main objective of endodontic treatment is complete cleaning and shaping of canals followed by three dimensional seal with no discomfort to patients. For both patients and clinicians, endodontic origin pain has been a major concern.²

Numerous strategies, such as different mechanical instrumentation techniques, irrigation techniques and intracanal medications, have been implemented to decrease the number of bacteria from the root canal system.^{3,4,5}

Calcium hydroxide is considered to be the first choice of root canal dressing material. Antimicrobial activity, tissue dissolving

capacity, and hard tissue development are few of its biological characteristics.⁶

Enterococcus faecalis is the predominant bacterium in resistant endodontic infections; the addition of calcium hydroxide finds this difficult to overcome.

Triple antibiotic paste (TAP) is the preferred intracanal medication in these situations. TAP, which includes minocycline, metronidazole, and ciprofloxacin, was initially utilized and launched by Hoshino. Clindamycin has been used in place of minocycline because it discolors teeth. These days, this modified triple antibiotic paste (M-TAP) is widely used.⁷

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Since there has been an increase in the incidence of antibiotic overuse & cytotoxic reaction there is growing increase in the use of herbal products.⁸⁻⁹

Curcuma longa (CL), a perennial herb and member of the Zingiberaceae (ginger) family, The primary component derived from turmeric roots, curcumin, has anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and anticancer properties. Several authors have used CL as an intracanal medication, pulpotomy medication, or root canal irrigant with encouraging outcomes.¹⁰

This study evaluate and compare the efficacy of three intracanal medicaments i.e., M-TAP, Calcium hydroxide and curcumin in pain reduction during endodontic treatment in symptomatic irreversible pulpitis using Visual Analog Scale.

Material and Method

In this study total 64 maxillary central incisors, lateral incisors or canines were randomly selected from the patients undergoing non surgical root canal treatment in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, at Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre, Gwalior. Written informed consent was taken from each patients who participated in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patient should be more than 18 year of age.
- Patient diagnosed teeth with acute or chronic apical periodontitis with irreversible pulpitis.
- Single rooted teeth i.e. maxillary central incisors, lateral incisors or canines.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patient with periodontally compromised teeth
- Patient teeth with open apex
- Patient teeth with granuloma
- Patient teeth with cyst
- Patient presenting with swelling and abscess in teeth.
- Patient tooth with incomplete root formation
- Patients who are taking analgesic, antibiotic or anti-inflammatory drugs during the 7 days prior to the treatment

Teeth that had acute pain on percussion and palpation but had minimal apical changes on the radiograph, such as periodontal ligament widening or minimal bone resorption in the apical area, were classified as having symptomatic apical periodontitis and were included in the study.

Pre-operative pain score recording using VAS

Thereafter, the patients were given the information about VAS and asked to record their preoperative pain score on VAS. Preoperative pain was recorded, with each patient given pain scale chart (VAS) in order to record his/her pain level before any intervention. The pain was recorded on a scale of 0-10. Pain intensity categorized as-

- No Pain (0)
- Mild Pain (1-3)
- Moderate Pain (4-6)
- Severe Pain (7-10)

Figure 1: VAS (Visual Analog Scale)

The access cavity was prepared using a high speed endo access bur (Dentsply Maillefer, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA). The glide path was prepared with stainless steel hand K-files, #06, #08, and #10 (MANI, Tochigi, Japan). Working length was determined by K file (MANI, Tochigi, Japan) using an electronic apex locator (Root ZX mini, J Morita, Tokyo, Japan) at the “0.5” mark then was confirmed with radiovisiography (RVG), to be 0.5–1 mm, shorter than radiographic apex. The root canal preparation was carried out to #20 (0.02 taper) with a hand K-file. The apical portion of the canal was enlarged using K-file to size 3 file larger than the initial apical file and the rest of the canal were prepared using step back technique.

During instrumentation, copious irrigation with 3% NaOCl (Neelkanth Ortho Dent Private Limited, Jodhpur, India) was carried out and the canals were flooded with 17% EDTA (Prime Dental Products Private Limited, Maharashtra, India) for 3 min. post root canal preparation, to remove the inorganic component of the smear layer. 5 mL saline solution was used between NaOCl and EDTA for a more efficient action of the chemical on the tissue.

Following instrumentation & irrigation canals was dried using sterile paper point and Intracanal medicaments was placed into the canal using Lentulospiral (Mani, Inc., Utsunomiya, Tochigi, Japan) and the patients were divided into four groups that are as follows:

- GROUP I (n=16): No intracanal medicament was placed. A dry cotton pellet was be placed (negative control group) and the access opening was sealed with Temporary filling material.
- GROUP II (n=16): The whole length of the Lentulo spiral was coated with the calcium hydroxide paste (Neocal Orikam) and inserted up to 1 mm from working length using low speed handpiece. The procedure was repeated until the paste extruded from the canal orifice indicating adequate fill.
- GROUP III (n=16): M-TAP was prepared by removing the coating of tablets and weighing on a digital machine (ATOM

Selves Enterprises) and crushing the equal amount of Ciprofloxacin (Ciplox 500mg, Cipla, India), Metronidazole (Flagyl 400mg, Abbott, India) & Clindamycin (Dalacin C 300mg, Pfizer Limited) tablets separately using mortar and pestle. M-TAP was mixed in the ratio 1:1:1. A total of 100mg of this modified triple antibiotic mixture will be dispensed and mixed with a drop of propylene glycol and polyethylene glycol (Purenso Global) to get a thick paste like consistency. This paste was inserted into the canal using lentulospiral.

- GROUP IV (n=16): Curcumin gel (Curenex gel Abbott, India) was inserted into the root canal using lentulospiral.

In all medicament groups excess medicaments coronal to the cementoenamel junction were removed with a moist cotton pellet, followed by placement of a sterile dry cotton pellet in the pulp chamber. Subsequently, the cavity was sealed with Temporary filling material. (OraFil-G Prevest Den Pro, Jammu, India) The teeth were ground out of occlusion to prevent pain from occlusal forces and the cycle was repeated as stated above.

Post-operative pain score recording

All study participants were given pain evaluation sheets and instructed to record their pain scores at designated time points i.e. post operatively at 24 h, and then every day till the seventh day. In addition, the operator made a telephonic call to every patient and recorded their post-operative pain scores at designated observation time points. Patients were recalled after 7 days along with the evaluation sheets. At this time, pain scores obtained from the patient and values telephonically recorded by the operator were compared. No oral medication was prescribed to the patient postoperatively unless the pain was severe which required intervention and the patient to be eliminated from the study.

Figure 2: Pre-operative Radiograph

figure 3: Access Opening

Figure 4: Working Length Determination

figure 5: Working Length Confirmed Radiographically

Figure 6: Placement of Intracanal Medicament Using Lentulospiral

Results

The data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS Version 26; Chicago Inc., IL, USA). Data comparison was done by applying specific statistical tests to find out the statistical significance of the comparisons.

The pair wise comparison of VAS scores on the 7th day showed statistically significant differences between some groups ($p < 0.05$), indicating that pain relief varied slightly depending on the intra-canal medicament used.

- Group III (M-TAP) and Group IV (curcumin gel) both had complete pain relief, as indicated by the non-significant difference between them ($p = 1.000$, NS), confirming that both medicaments were equally effective in eliminating pain by the 7th day.
- Group I (no medicament) showed significantly higher residual pain compared to all other groups, with mean

differences of 0.56 when compared to Group III ($p = 0.000$) and Group IV ($p = 0.000$), reinforcing its inferior pain management.

- Group II (calcium hydroxide) had lower pain levels than Group I, but the difference was only moderately significant ($p = 0.031$), suggesting a slower but eventual reduction in pain. However, it was not significantly different from M-TAP or curcumin gel ($p = 0.492$), indicating that by the 7th day, its effect was comparable to the more effective medicaments.

By the 7th day, M-TAP and curcumin gel had completely eliminated pain, confirming their superior efficacy in post-endodontic pain management. Calcium hydroxide also showed effective pain reduction, although its effect was slightly delayed. The control group (no medicament) exhibited the slowest pain resolution, reinforcing the necessity of an intra-canal medicament for effective pain management. These findings further highlight M-TAP and curcumin gel as the most effective intra-canal medicaments for long-term pain relief.

Parameter	Group I (n=16)	Group II (n=16)	Group III (n=16)	Group IV (n=16)	p-value
Age (Mean \pm SD)	35.00 \pm 9.80	32.12 \pm 6.60	32.37 \pm 10.07	30.50 \pm 7.39	0.527 (NS)
Gender (Male/Female)	8/8	9/7	9/7	8/8	0.969 (NS)
Pre-Operative VAS Score (Mean \pm SD)	9.06 \pm 1.57	9.06 \pm 1.43	9.12 \pm 1.45	9.00 \pm 1.59	0.997 (NS)

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Time Interval	Group I (Mean \pm SD)	Group II (Mean \pm SD)	Group III (Mean \pm SD)	Group IV (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
24 Hours	8.31 \pm 1.19	8.06 \pm 1.12	5.87 \pm 0.88	7.68 \pm 1.25	0.000*
2nd Day	7.00 \pm 1.09	6.93 \pm 1.06	3.31 \pm 0.47	6.00 \pm 0.51	0.000*
3rd Day	6.25 \pm 0.77	5.50 \pm 0.51	1.06 \pm 0.85	5.00 \pm 0.51	0.000*
4th Day	5.12 \pm 0.61	4.12 \pm 0.80	0.00 \pm 0.00	2.81 \pm 0.40	0.000*
5th Day	3.68 \pm 0.70	2.62 \pm 0.50	0.00 \pm 0.00	1.25 \pm 0.57	0.000*
6th Day	1.12 \pm 0.71	0.50 \pm 0.73	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.000*
7th Day	0.56 \pm 0.62	0.18 \pm 0.40	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.000*

Table 2: Comparative Evaluation of VAS Scores Over Time

Discussion

The most painful dental procedure is usually thought to be a root canal treatment. It is challenging to discover whether a single or a combination of factors cause pain in a clinical trial. The host bacteria relationship, microbial interactions, or the presence of clearly pathogenic bacteria prior to treatment may exacerbate a residual infection if a root canal was not debrided correctly.¹¹

A medicament an antimicrobial agent is inserted into the root canal in an effort to eradicate any remaining microbes and prevent reinfection. Thus, they can be used to control inflammatory root resorption, eradicate apical exudates, kill bacteria, lessen inflam-

mation, and avoid contamination in between sessions.

VAS ratings were divided into four categories: 0 for no pain, 1–3 for mild pain, 4–6 for moderate pain, and 7–10 for severe pain. This was done to help the patient comprehend the pain scale more precisely and quantitatively.¹²

A study by Prasad et al.¹³ evaluated the effectiveness of calcium hydroxide (CH) and triple antibiotic paste (TAP) as an intracanal medicament in pain reduction. This study signifies that patients undergoing endodontic therapy with TAP carry high significant (twice) results in pain reduction with each visits.

According to Swati Pai et al.¹⁴ Calcium hydroxide and triple antibiotic paste are effective for managing inter-appointment flare ups in diabetic patients. When it comes to preventing diabetes flare ups, triple antibiotic paste works better than calcium hydroxide.

A study by Mittal R et al.¹⁵ compared and evaluated the antibacterial efficacy of calcium hydroxide (CH) paste, triple antibiotic paste (TAP), and double antibiotic paste (DAP) and concluded that TAP and DAP have similar antimicrobial efficacy though better than CH.

Chandwani et al.¹⁶ has conducted research to assess and contrast the antibacterial effectiveness of triple antibiotic paste (TAP) with bromelain and calcium hydroxide (CaOH)₂ against *Enterococcus faecalis* bacteria. Bromelain's antibacterial efficacy against *E. faecalis* was found to be comparable to TAP and more effective than Ca(OH)₂ paste

Khan AM et al.¹⁷ evaluated the effects of triple antibiotic paste, calcium hydroxide, and chlorhexidine on pain following root canal therapy. Post-operatively, patients were asked to rate their pain on the Wong Baker FACES pain rating scale at 4, 48, 72, and 96 hours. When used as an intracanal medicine on necrotic teeth with apical periodontitis symptoms, triple antibiotic paste demonstrated efficient pain management.

The concern of the TAP is that it may cause bacterial resistance. To overcome this, disadvantage of TAP, Curcumin was introduced.

In vitro studies have compared CL with CH and found its antibacterial efficacy against *E. faecalis* to be either superior to CH or equivalent to it.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ Prabhakar et al. stated that it is effective in inhibition of *E. faecalis*. In addition, it has no adverse effect on root dentin microhardness compared to CH.

Upadhyay K²⁰ et al demonstrated that Turmeric extract has substantial its antibacterial efficacy against all important root canal pathogens.

A study conducted by Eskandarinezhad M et al²¹ showed that antibacterial effects of calcium hydroxide, curcumin as an intracanal medicament on 6-week old *Enterococcus faecalis* biofilm in which curcumin had the most significant effect, followed by calcium hydroxide.

Within the limitations of this study, it is recommended to use the M-TAP intracanal medicaments in symptomatic apical periodontitis, which could lead to efficient pain relief post-operatively.

Very few studies have been conducted on Curcumin. The antibacterial effect of Curcumin as an intracanal medicament is still unknown. Further clinical trials with large sample sizes, using different vehicles, including multi-rooted teeth, different preoperative diagnoses and evaluation of antibacterial effectiveness are recommended to draw definitive clinical conclusions.

Further in vivo and immunological studies are needed to identify the exact mechanism by which the M-TAP resulted in decreasing postoperative pain and to determine the cytotoxic effect of M-TAP.

Conclusion

M-TAP paste as an intracanal medicament was more effective in pain reduction followed by Curcumin and calcium hydroxide during multi-visit root canal treatment. As this study has a limited observational period, further studies are to be conducted with extended observational periods.

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